

WAYS TO OPTIMIZE SERVICE MANAGEMENT IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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Abstract : Economy innovative in development Uzbekistan in the Republic tourism of the field in development normative-legal of documents held place according to scientific recommendations work from exit consists of

Key words : Tourism industry , national economy , tourism potential , gross internal product , foreign tourists , marketing research , currency

Today, comprehensive measures are being implemented in the country to develop tourism as one of the strategic sectors that ensure the diversification of the national economy, the rapid development of regions, the creation of new jobs, the increase of incomes and living standards of the population, and the increase of the country's investment attractiveness. Liberalization of the visa regime, simplification of the procedure for registration of foreign citizens, granting of privileges and preferences for the development of the tourism network made it possible to effectively promote the potential of national tourism in domestic and foreign markets.

First of all, creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism in the private sector, increasing the competitiveness and quality of the services provided, actively and comprehensively promoting the national tourism product in the world market, all this is in accordance with the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

Legislation and legal framework in the field of tourism activities aimed at creating favorable conditions for the activities of tourism industry subjects are being formed. Eliminate all obstacles and pitfalls in the development of tourism, visa and registration procedures, Simplification of passport and customs control, government management of the tourism sector, and market-specific regulation mechanism are being optimized, which determines the relevance of graduation qualification work.

Theoretical and methodological problems of various aspects of tourism development are studied in economic literature. Theoretical and practical questions on special problems of socio-economic relations of tourism development are reflected in scientific works and researches of scientists from far and near foreign countries. Special issues regarding the development of the tourism sector in the conditions of Uzbekistan are covered in the scientific works and researches of a number of our economists. In particular, K.Kh. Abdurakhmonov, M.R. Boltabayev, I.S. Tukhliyev, M.T. Alimova, E.V. Golysheva, M.Q. Pardayev, B.Sh. Safarov, Z.O. Rakhimov, T. Tashmurotov, N. Tukhliyev, H.M. Mamatkulov, B.Kh. Turayev, D.K. Usmanova, N.E. Ibadullayev, A. .Eshtayev and others.

To achieve the set goal, the following tasks were set and implemented:

- Looking at the socio-economic nature and importance of the development of tourism in Uzbekistan;
- Elucidate the priority directions of regulation and development of national tourism;
- Looking at the role of tourism development committee in Uzbekistan in management and regulation of tourism;
- Looking at the concept of development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025 and its possibilities in the development of the sector;
- Explain the importance of free tourist zones in the development of tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Until January 1, 2022, the income of qualified foreign specialists employed as hotel managers is exempted from the income tax of individuals from the payment fund for the labor of qualified foreign specialists. a favorable economic, administrative and legal environment was created for the rapid development of the tourism sector.

Increasing the number of ATMs and terminals working with international payment systems at airports, railway stations, hotels and other tourist facilities, as well as accepting payments to business entities in foreign currency, including the introduction of contactless electronic payments additional amenities are being created.

By 2025, it is planned to increase the share of tourism in the gross domestic product of Uzbekistan from 2.3 percent (2017) to 5 percent, and the number of foreign tourists to 9-10 million, including the number of tourists from distant foreign countries to 2 million. It is also expected to increase the volume of tourism exports from 950 million dollars to 2.2 billion dollars. It is planned to release the number of location vehicles from 850 to 3000. The number of tour operators is expected to almost double from 860. It is also planned to increase the number of local tourists almost twice - from 14 million to 25 million within the framework of the program aimed at the development of domestic tourism called "Travel around Uzbekistan".

In the conditions of the development of market relations and the creation of an environment of free competition, the increase in demand for tourism is a natural process. Building hotels that suit the taste of tourists, paying great attention to advertising of historical monuments, improving tourism services, thoroughly researching tourists in every way and organizing events will lead to the development of tourism.

Due to the foreign currency inflow into the budget, tourism will also affect the development of other sectors of the economy, the infrastructure of the regions, the creation of new jobs, and the restoration of the historical and cultural heritage

of the Uzbek people. There are opportunities for this in our country, increasing the number of new high-quality tourist facilities and thus improving the country's economy requires the implementation of a number of measures. In this regard:

- Organization of marketing research in the tourism system;
- Improvement of tourism service;
- adaptation to world standards;
- Development of the type and quality of tourist excursion services;
- Advertising of historical monuments and monuments;
- Finding and organizing new tourist places;
- Increasing and improving the types of additional services;
- Improving the work of all sectors related to tourism: household services, communication, transport and transportation;
- When determining the price, take into account the conjuncture of the tourism market;
- Choosing the right employees.

In our opinion, regularly conducting marketing research in the tourism market, taking into account the conjuncture in demand, supply, pricing, studying tourism in different countries of the world will lead to high-quality and positive results in this field.

To show that the visa regime, the rules of stay in Uzbekistan and the procedure for conducting business activities have been simplified, the development of infrastructure in the tourism sector and the measures taken to promote tourism potential as important factors for doubling the number of incoming foreign tourists in 2018 including:

- the visa-free regime has been introduced in an additional 9 (total 18) countries, and the number of countries that have introduced a simplified procedure for issuing entry visas to their citizens has increased from 12 to 50;
- the system of issuing and submitting electronic entry visas has been launched, the procedure for visa-free entry, temporary stay and exit through citizen transfer

points has been introduced for citizens of 101 countries transiting the territory of Uzbekistan;

- the procedure for temporary registration of foreign citizens on the territory of the republic has been simplified, this procedure has been transferred to a fully electronic form through the E-MEHMON system;
- cancellation of guest house certification procedure;
- The introduction of a new mechanism for the certification of tourist class motor vehicles intended for the transportation of 8 or more passengers imported into the territory of the republic is an example of the increasingly perfected tourism legislation.

The development of market relations and the creation of an environment of free competition is a natural process in which the demand for tourism increases in all sectors. A significant share of income in the economy of all developed countries falls on tourism. Building hotels that suit the taste of tourists, paying great attention to advertising of historical monuments, improving tourism services, thoroughly researching tourists in every way and organizing events will lead to the development of tourism.

With the development of international tourism, many people are provided with work in some countries. International tourism not only generates foreign exchange gains, but it can transform old but historic places with few inhabitants into large and developed cities.

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